

Relationship between ABO blood group and COVID-19: A review of the report associated with asthmatic patient

ABSTRACT

Introduction and objectives: The COVID-19's causative agent, the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV2), first surfaced in late 2019 and spread quickly over the world, posing a threat to global health that resulted in roughly 70 million cumulative cases in just one year (WHO et al., 2020). Despite the COVID-19 vaccines' recent clearance and use, the goal of herd immunity is still far from being a global reality

Methods: Before starting the review, the author came up with the aforementioned subjects. In order to get the answers to these questions, a search was done on PubMed and Google Scholar for articles mentioning severe asthma and COVID-19, ABO blood group and infectious disorders, COVID-19, or SARSCoV-2 up to June 2022. The keywords "severe asthma," "ABO blood group," "COVID-19," or "SARS-CoV2" were all part of the search strategy. The study topic then used narrative reconstruction to combine the data. Because the body of data in this area is still developing, no restrictions on study type were used in the inclusion process. The references that were deemed to have material pertinent to the predetermined queries were all included.

Results: Upper respiratory cell infection is the first stage of the COVID-19 disease mechanisms. Subsequently, various immunological components, including cell-mediated immunity and antibody formation, are activated, adding to the disease's severity. Despite being rare in the COVID-19 course, certain Patients experience a cytokine storm that damages their organs and can result in abrupt respiratory failure. multiorgan failure or the distress syndrome. To address the association more robustly, more observational studies are required that use large-scale samples, take into account conflicting variables, and account for blood group distribution in society. Additionally, research is required to comprehend the mechanisms underlying the beneficial or detrimental impact of blood groups on COVID-19 infection in those with asthma.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19's causative agent, the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV2), first surfaced in late 2019 and spread quickly over the world, posing a threat to global health that resulted in roughly 70 million cumulative cases in just one year (WHO et al., 2020). Despite the COVID-19 vaccines' recent clearance and use, the goal of herd immunity is still far from being a global reality. The novel severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) that causes COVID-19 is to blame for the significant rise in pneumonia hospitalizations with multiorgan illness (Anderson et al., 2020). When COVID-19 initially surfaced in December 2019, it had already spread to nearly every nation on the planet by the end of 2020, causing more than 79 million illnesses and more than 1.9 million fatalities. Why the clinical presentation can vary so much, from moderate and even asymptomatic to severe clinical diseases like pneumonia, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), organ dysfunction, and even death, is unknown (Parasher A. et al., 2021). Nevertheless, there has been a quest for additional biological markers that could predict susceptibility to SARS-CoV-2 infection and the likelihood of catastrophic outcomes due to the poorly understood pathophysiology of COVID-19 and the diversity in clinical presentation and outcomes (T.P. Velavan et al., 2021 and D. Ellinghaus et al., 2020)

The ABO blood group is made up of discrete carbohydrate epitopes on the surface of blood cells and other organs, such as the respiratory and gastrointestinal epithelium (S. Marionneau, et al., 2001). According to some scientists, the ABO blood group may be a biological indicator of COVID-19 susceptibility, with group O individuals having a decreased risk of infection (Zaho J et al., 2020). Cells of specific endothelium and epithelial tissues, including the respiratory system, express ABO antigenic antigens. While group O is typically associated with stronger disease resistance, the presence of A and B antigens is linked to increased vulnerability to infections, cardiovascular conditions, and cancer (Gillmiyarova FN, et al., 2020)

In patients, asthma severity and control are two distinct yet connected domains. Inappropriate therapy, non-adherence, overtreatment, side effects, and other treatment-related factors, as well as the presence of underlying risk factors (Quirce S, et al., 2011), most notably viral respiratory infection, are linked to worsening symptoms and asthma exacerbations. Exacerbations of asthma brought on by respiratory illnesses or other disorders have a detrimental effect on the patient's health and worsen their prognosis. (Ritchie AI, et al., 2016)

Numerous research have looked into a potential connection between the ABO blood group and SARS-CoV-2 infection since the initial report (J. Zhao, et L., 2021), with varying results. ABO blood type has been mentioned by certain authors as having an impact on SARS-CoV-2 infection. Others, however, were unable to show these connections (S. Dzik, et al., 2020 and A. Khalil, et al., 2020). Blood types A and O have generally been associated with lower and higher risks, respectively, of contracting SARS-CoV-2, respectively. It is notable that a previous study on SARS-CoV found a negative correlation between blood type O and infection among a sample of healthcare professionals (Y. Cheng, et al., 2020).

Clinically, COVID-19 can range in severity from modest to extremely severe, resulting in patient fatality in some cases (WHO et al., 2020). Undoubtedly, the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic poses a significant challenge for the world's health systems. Since the start of the pandemic, a link has been hypothesized between the severity of COVID-19 and long-term illnesses such as high blood pressure, diabetes mellitus, and cardiovascular disease. However, COVID-19's effect on asthma patients has been less pronounced than that of influenza and other seasonal viruses (Chow EJ, et al., 2015). , it is imperative to characterize the clinical course of SARS-CoV-2 infection in patients with asthma, relation to their blood groups, and assess the impact of asthma and asthma-related comorbidities and treatment in COVID-19-related outcomes.

Population-based registries with actual data from the real world are the ideal tools for understanding new and fast developing diseases like COVID-19 (Mallappallil M, et al., 2020). In this setting, fusing big data analytics with real-world data has the potential to improve our comprehension of the impacts of COVID-19 in asthma patients in relation to their ABO blood groups and uncover fresh approaches and choices for therapeutic intervention.

Of the almost 400 million asthmatics worldwide, 310% have severe asthma, however this condition is linked to higher hospitalization and mortality rates, decreased quality of life, and higher healthcare expenses (Agache I, et al., 2020). The impact of COVID-19 on underlying disorders, including severe asthma, is currently unclear to authorities and medical professionals.

Although respiratory viruses are among the most frequent causes of asthma flare-ups, not all of these viruses have a same impact on patients. The information that is now available is rather contradictory as to whether persons with asthma similar to a particular blood group are more likely to contract SARS-CoV-2 or develop severe manifestations of the disease (Joao Gaspar-Marques, et al., 2021)

There have been a number of publications published about the association between COVID-19, ABO blood group, and asthma, but there hasn't been a recent evaluation of the unique characteristics and novelty of severe asthma. The author seek to review five alternative research issues about potential connections between these disease entities, taking into account the complexity of severe asthma pathophysiology and the expanding information of COVID-19:

Overview of the ABO Blood Group

Severity of the ABO and COVID-19 diseases

Relationship between ABO blood group and Asthma

COVID-19 and the epidemiology of severe asthma

METHODS

Before starting the review, the author came up with the aforementioned subjects. In order to get the answers to these questions, a search was done on PubMed and Google Scholar for articles mentioning severe asthma and COVID-19, ABO blood group and infectious disorders, COVID-19, or SARSCoV-2 up to June 2022. The keywords "severe asthma," "ABO blood group," "COVID-19," or "SARS-CoV2" were all part of the search strategy. The study topic then used narrative reconstruction to combine the data. Because the body of data in this area is still developing, no restrictions on study type were used in the inclusion process. The references that were deemed to have material pertinent to the predetermined queries were all included.

Overview of the ABO Blood Group

The four main blood types identified by the ABO blood group system are A, B, AB, and O. The ABO system is clinically the most significant of the ISBT's 39 recognized blood group systems and 350 recognized antigens (Piccinni MP, et. al., 2020 and Yamamoto F, et. al., 2020). Over O, the A and B antigens are inherited jointly more frequently (Dean L. et. al., and Bethesda et. al., 2005). Blood types AB and O are determined by the presence of both or neither of the homonymous antigens, whereas blood types A and B are determined by the presence of just one (X. Dai, et. al., 2020). ABO antigens were initially identified in red blood cells (RBCs), but were later discovered in a variety of tissues and secretions, including saliva, intestinal mucosa, and endothelium (L. Cooling, et al., 2015), and the respiratory tract epithelium (S. Marionneau et al., 2001). The ABH antigens are oligosaccharides that are exposed on RBCs and other cells, as well as in bodily secretions (the H antigen determines the O blood type). Allelic genes that encode glycosyltransferases, which transfer monosaccharides to the non-reducing ends of particular glycans on glycoproteins and glycolipids, determine the A and B antigens. This monosaccharide is N-acetyl-D-galactosamine for A and Dgalactose for B. The corresponding A and B glycosyltransferases are absent or have been inactivated in group O individuals due to one of several polymorphisms, causing the non-reducing ends of the the H antigen is expressed by the appropriate glycans. (Ruchika Goel, et. al., 2021)

The expression of the homonymous antigens is controlled by alleles A and B, which codominate over allele O. Recessive allele O, on the other hand, has no effect on the expression of any antigen. Antigens A and B are secondary products of the ABO gene, which primarily encodes enzymes that catalyze the addition of monosaccharide motifs to an oligosaccharide backbone that is attached to glycoproteins or glycolipids through N- or O-linked glycosylation. Like carbohydrates, antigens A and B are secondary products of the ABO gene. Antigen H, the acceptor of antigens A and B at the expanding oligosaccharide chain, is necessary for this process (L. Cooling, et. al., 2015, J. Le Pendu and F. Yamamoto, et. al., 2004).

In the first few months of life, this system's antibodies (i.e., anti-A and anti-B) develop. These antibodies are typically "naturally occurring" antibodies produced in response to contact with non-self A and/or B antigens, which are frequently present in food and microorganisms, particularly the gut microbiota (Holodick NE, et. al., 2020). Nearly all healthy people who lack the

corresponding antigen also circulate anti-A and anti-B, often of the IgM isotype; IgG anti-A,B is frequently seen in group O persons (Gerard C et. al., and Stussi G et. al). Because the matching IgM antibodies bind complement effectively, inducing intravascular hemolysis of the transfused RBCs and activation of coagulation, transfusion of ABO-incompatible RBCs can produce severe haemolytic transfusion responses. Because of the extremely high density of ABH antigens on RBCs, anti-A and/or anti-B IgG molecules are in close proximity to one another on the RBC surface, which causes complement activation and severe intravascular hemolysis (Dean L. et. al., and Bethesda et. al., 2005). This medical emergency can result in severe renal failure, disseminated intravascular coagulation, and death if left untreated. Therefore, a key component of contemporary blood banking systems and procedures is to always transfuse RBCs that are ABO compatible.

Severity of the ABO and COVID-19 diseases

Analysis is also necessary regarding how ABO type affects the severity of COVID-19 disease. A statistically significant correlation between thrombotic problems and ICU admission with blood group was found in a study (Zalba Marcos S, et al., 2020) on infection and thrombosis related with COVID-19 and the potential role of the ABO blood group. Group B experienced more thrombosis (28.6%), required more ICU admission (38.1%), and had an OR of 6.16 (1.75, 21.8). Group O had the fewest ICU admissions. Fibrinogen increased much more in groups AB-B than in and D-dimer increases higher in group A compared to O (significant difference; beta = 2392.7). There were no variations in complications related to bleeding. As a result, group O patients in one trial had a decreased probability of hospitalization for SARS-CoV-2 infection compared to group A patients (J. Li, et. al., 2020). However, a multivariate analysis did not account for the fact that group A patients had higher comorbid risk factors for severe illness. Another team conducted a GWAS on COVID-19 patients who had respiratory failure [57], finding a cross-replicating association at 9q34 that was statistically significant. A blood type-specific examination of the 9q34 signal, which was found at the ABO blood group locus, revealed that group A people had a higher risk of developing severe COVID-19 with respiratory failure and group O people had a protective effect.

Another illustration is that patients with blood group A or AB had a higher risk of needing mechanical ventilation, continuous renal replacement therapy, and prolonged intensive care unit admission when compared to group O or B in a nested prospective observational study of critically ill patients with COVID-19 in Canada. B sufferers [Hoiland RL et al., 2020]. Another recent retrospective cohort analysis with around 500,000 Danish people tested for SARS-CoV-2 revealed decreased prevalence of SARS-CoV-2 infection in those with blood group O. The ABO blood group was found to be a risk factor for SARS-CoV-2 infection in this investigation, but not for COVID-19 hospitalization or death (Barnkob MB et al., 202).

In a recent study on Japanese people (Kusumoto, et. al., 2022) In the COVID-19 group compared to the control group, blood group A was significantly more common (41.6% vs. 36.8%) and blood group O was significantly less common (26.2% vs. 30.8%). Furthermore, the COVID-19 group had a considerably lower prevalence of the genotype OO. Additionally, compared to blood group O, blood group AB was found to be an independent risk factor for the majority of serious diseases

[aOR (95% CI) = 1.84 (1.00-3.37)]. Similar to this, only genotype AB was a distinct risk factor for the most severe disease when compared to genotype OO in the ABO genotyping study.

While other researchers (A. Khalil et al., and M.A. Ozkarafakili et al., 2022) were unable to replicate substantial relationships between ABO blood type and SARS-CoV-2 infection, others did so for blood types other than A and O. A meta-analysis revealed that blood type B is linked to a greater risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection in Asian cohorts but not in European cohorts (T. Kander, et al., 2022). Blood type B was linked to a considerably higher risk of SARS-CoV-2 infection in various studies (M.A. Almadhi et al., and D. Jawdat, et al., 2022). In turn, AB blood type has been strongly associated with either a higher (M.B. Barnkob et al., 2020 or N. Liu, et al., 2021) or a decreased (M.A. Almadhi et al., and J. Gamboa-aguilar et al., 2021) chance of contracting COVID-19.

Together, these results imply that group O persons may have a lower risk of COVID-19 severe disease and SARS-CoV-2 infection than non-group O individuals. However, these findings are not conclusive, and additional research is necessary.

Relationship between ABO blood group and Asthma

In another study between association of asthma and blood group, Most (40.3%) of the participants were between 20 and 29 years old, the majority (56.9%) were females. Among participants, 19.2% were suffering from asthma. The distribution of ABO blood group was as follows: blood group O (44.7%), blood group A (26.2%), blood group B (21.4%), and blood group AB (7.7%). The proportions of Rhesus (D) positive and Rhesus (D) negative were 85.6% and 14.4%, respectively. The results showed an insignificant relationship between bronchial asthma and ABO blood group, Rhesus factor, gender, body mass index group, and marital status ($p > 0.05$), while it showed a significant relationship between bronchial asthma and age group ($p < 0.05$) (Mohammed Abdullah S. Alkhidhr et al, 2019). The ABO phenotypic frequencies in children with asthma are similar, according to Ronchetti et al. (Ronchetti F et al., 2001). Regarding ABO & Rh blood groups, a different study finds no significant differences between asthma patients and controls (Dhiman SR et al). Another study on 344 patients with bronchial asthma and 7,518 healthy adults in Najaf Governorate found that the percentage of blood group (O) individuals with bronchial asthma was 49.12%, whereas the percentages for blood groups A, B, and AB were 25%, 23.8%, and 2.03%, respectively (Dhiman SR et al). No significant changes were found in the percentages of Rh in the control and asthmatic groups, and there was a substantial rise in the prevalence of bronchial asthma in blood group (O), but not in the other blood groups (A, B, or AB) (Dhiman SR et al). In their study of 228 coal workers who had asthma, Kauffmann et al. (Kauffmann F, Frette C, et al) found a strong correlation between asthma and blood-type O's non-secretor phenotype.

Contrarily, in a different study from Nigeria, 200 asthmatic patients and 100 individuals served as the control group. Of these, 37% belonged to blood type A, 28% to blood group B, 13% to blood group AB, and 22% to blood group O (Alo MN et al). Out of 200 study participants, 90.5% of the Rh blood group participants are Rh positive and 9.5% are Rh negative. This result shows that blood group A is more prevalent and statistically significant among asthmatic patients ($p < 0.05$), but there

was no statistical difference between the Rh system in study participants with asthma and controls (Alo MN et al). This concurs with the findings of De la Vega et al. (De la Vega AR et al), who found that asthmatic patients had a high prevalence of blood group A, but that there was no difference in the Rh systems in the two groups (study subjects and controls). In same study, it was also discovered that there was a highly significant variation in the distribution of blood groups A and O between the control and asthmatic groups (De la Vega AR et al),. Boys are more likely than girls to get asthma, although following puberty, women are somewhat more likely than men to experience asthma (Shiva Prasad HN et al). We discovered that 44.7% of asthmatic patients were men and 55.3% were women. Another survey, however, found that men outnumbered women by a large margin of 55.5% to 44.5% (Bijanzadeh M et al).

COVID-19 and the epidemiology of severe asthma

A global public health emergency was driven on by the COVID-19 pandemic brought on by infections with the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus. Due to the fact that COVID-19 disease can affect both the upper and lower airways, the connections between SARS-CoV-2 are not a surprise. Soon it was discovered that the lung inflammation was severe and pre-existing. Particularly in SARS-CoV-2 lung epithelial cell datasets Transcriptomic analysis of infection and idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis Analyses identified several common pathways and hub genes (Taz TA et al., 2021). Similar findings suggest that SARS-CoV-2 is genetically related. Respiratory artery hypertension (Taz TA et al., 2021). It is widely acknowledged that individuals with respiratory allergies and asthma are more vulnerable to and more severely affected by viral infections (Corne JM et al). As a result, asthma was first thought to be a risk factor for COVID-19, and it has been noted that COVID-19 hospitalized patients have a greater prevalence of asthma (Khawaja AP et al). Patients with COVID-19 were shown to have an increased risk of morbidity when they had asthma (Choi HG et al). However, according to several research (Wang JY et al and Avdeev S et al), asthma prevalence in COVID-19 individuals is lower than anticipated. This suggests that having asthma may have some protective effects (Carli G et al). According to certain data, asthma is not linked to COVID-19 results (Beken B et al and Kim S. et al). The connection between COVID-19 and asthma is still debatable and disputed as of right now (Johnston SL et al, Morais-Almeida M et al and Song J et al).

Only 14 out of 676 patients (2.1%) in the Belgian Severe Asthma Registry (Hanon S. et al) had SARS-CoV-2 infection verified by a positive PCR or serology test. According to these results, the incidence was lower than the population's average (5.1%). The incidence of COVID-19 did not statistically differ between patients who received biologic treatment and those who did not. On this cohort of patients with severe asthma, COVID-19 was not linked to any fatalities.

Seven out of 558 participants (1.25%) with severe asthma in the Italian Registry of Severe Asthma (IRSA) (Antonicelli L. et al) acquired COVID-19. There were no recorded fatalities, and the hospitalization rate for COVID19-infected people with severe asthma was comparable to that of the general population. Compared to those treated with ICSLABA alone, patients on biologics had

a higher percentage of COVID-19 (5.43% vs. 0%), but there was no statistically significant difference.

According to a study, asthma has a surprisingly different protective impact from other common respiratory viral breakouts on the risk of COVID-19 infection and hospitalization. Notably, COVID-19 progression depends on 'cytokine storms' and overactive innate immunity. Asthma's characteristically allergic immune responses may be a factor in how well it protects against COVID-19. Our findings imply that genetic susceptibility to asthma is linked to a lower incidence of COVID-19 infection and hospitalization. This phenomena might be brought on by the continuous inflammatory reactions' protective effects against COVID-19's early phases (Baranova Ancha et al., 2022). There may not be enough evidence to prove that the connections found in observational research are causally related. As a result, it is critical to clarify the mechanisms behind the relationship between COVID-19 and asthma and to determine their correlation using more fundamental data (Baranova Ancha et al., 2022). The extensive and intricate immunological effects of SARS-CoV-2 infection add to the growing complexity of understanding about severe asthma. Regarding severe asthma endotypes, type 2 high appears to play a protective function in the progression of both COVID-19 and SARS-CoV-2 infection. Type-2 low, on the other hand, appears to enhance the chance of infection and serious disease types. Although this theory may be tenable from a theoretical perspective, more substantial evidence is required to support it. Although further research is required, biologics for severe asthma do not appear to raise the risk of infection or severe COVID-19, and they may even be protective. Major respiratory societies across the world advise continuing the biologic treatment, preferably in a self-administered home program, in the COVID-19 era. (Gaspar-Marques, J. et al). Although more research is required, biologics for severe COVID-19 do not appear to increase the risk of infection or severe COVID-19.

Discussion

In a study looking into ABO blood types and vulnerability 45 hospital employees who had encountered SARS in 2005. The patient was examined without any protective clothing. They were examined for IgG antibodies to SARS-CoV (Cheng Y et al). The findings indicated that people with blood group O were less likely to contract SARS; however, the findings for blood group B were not statistically significant and were undefined for blood groups A and AB (Cheng Y et al). Reverse transcriptase PCR and clinical diagnostic criteria, such as epidemic history or clinical symptoms and clinical features, were used to test cases in our included investigations (Chen J at al., Zeng X et al and Zietz M. et al). The above-mentioned study about cases of SARS-CoV in humans was consistent with the findings regarding cases of severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infection.

In the analysis, there was no statistically significant correlation between blood type and COVID-19 mortality. The mortality caused by COVID-19 is influenced by a variety of patient characteristics, including as gender, age, diabetes, asthma, and mother's health issues (Williamson EJ et al). Blood type, however, has no impact on mortality outcome.

To address the association more robustly, more observational studies are required that use large-scale samples, take into account conflicting variables, and account for blood group distribution in society. Additionally, research is required to comprehend the mechanisms underlying the beneficial or detrimental impact of blood groups on COVID-19 infection in those with asthma.

Conclusion

Additional research is needed to determine the role of ABO blood type in SARS-CoV-2 infectivity and COVID-19 infection in people with severe asthma, but mounting evidence points to a potential involvement for ABO blood type in disease biology at the biochemical and physiological levels. In addition, it is important to acknowledge that host variables, which have already been mentioned as having a significant impact on the severity of COVID-19, also play a significant role. In contrast, the significance of ABO type is probably secondary and unchangeable.

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